

Stability of Complexes of Penicillamine with Beryllium-, Copper-, Nickel-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Lead(II)

A. K. ROUL and R. K. PATNAIK*

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Rourkela-769 008

Manuscript received 11 August 1989, revised 23 March 1992, accepted 10 April 1992

Some of the metal chelates of penicillamine have been studied^{1,2}. The present work deals with the investigation on the formation of some penicillamine complexes with transitional metal ions and their possible dissociation.

Results and Discussion

The formation of 1 : 1 complexes in experiment-1 may be represented by equation (1),

where, H_2Pen and C represent penicillamine and complex respectively. Equilibrium constants (K)

of the reaction (1) have been calculated following the reported method³⁻⁵. k_1 and k_2 , the dissociation constants² of NH_3 and SH groups of penicillamine, are 1.32×10^{-8} and 3.72×10^{-11} respectively. The equilibrium constant (K) has been calculated below pH 6 where the number of protons (n) liberated is less than two. The mean values of $-\log K$ with their standard deviations are recorded in Table 1. In case of nickel-penicillamine system, the values of n exceeded 2 even at low pH, hence the values of K has not been calculated. In case of cadmium-penicillamine system, the values of K could not be determined due to the formation of precipitate.

At pH greater than 7.00, 7.50 and 6.70 for Pb, Ni and Zn systems respectively, the neutral complex C dissociates to C_1^- according to

The dissociation constant K_1 for the above reactions are calculated as before and the mean values of $-\log K_1$ with their standard deviations recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Metal	$-\log K$	$-\log K_1$	$\log K_2 / -\log K_3$	$-\log K_{1:2}$
Be	7.97 ± 0.02		0.37 ± 0.07	19.32 ± 0.09
Co	9.93 ± 0.07		1.74 ± 0.006^a	22.77 ± 0.09
Ni		8.14 ± 0.09	0.77 ± 0.05	15.62 ± 0.09
Zn	8.13 ± 0.06	8.21 ± 0.08	0.72 ± 0.06^a	18.23 ± 0.09
Cd			1.27 ± 0.09	
Pb	5.68 ± 0.06	8.12 ± 0.08	2.57 ± 0.006	19.48 ± 0.08

^aValues of $-\log K_3$.

The reaction in the experiment-2 can be represented as

The values of the equilibrium constants (K_2) for reaction (3) are calculated as before^{4,5} and the mean values of $\log K_2 / -\log K_3$ with their standard deviations are recorded in Table 1. The values of $-\log (K_2 \times k_1)$ agree well with those of $-\log K$ obtained earlier from experiment-1 which corroborates the results obtained from both the experiments.

The reaction taking place in the formation of 1 : 2 penicillamine complexes (experiment-3) can be represented as

The equilibrium constants $-\log K_{1:2}$ are calculated as before and the mean values of $-\log K_{1:2}$ with their standard deviations are tabulated in Table 1.

Penicillamine behaves like a dibasic acid. The formation of neutral complex is accompanied with the liberation of 2 protons. This indicates that penicillamine may coordinate to the metal ions through COO^- , NH_2 and SH groups and other coordination positions are occupied by water molecules. The dissociation of neutral complex is associated with the liberation of another proton from the coordinated water molecule.

The relative order of stability of 1 : 1 type penicillamine complexes is $Pb > Cd > Ni > Be > Zn > Co$, while that of 1 : 2 type complex is $Ni > Zn > Be > Pb > Co$. Similar order has been observed by Lenz and Martell². Klotz *et al.*⁶ also reported the order of affinity for the sulphhydryl group of bovine albumin as $Pb > Cd > Zn > Cu$ and Li and Manning⁷ reported the order of affinity for sulphhydryl group in case of cysteine and small molecules as $Pb > Cd > Zn$.

The relative order of stability reported here is very similar to those obtained by other authors.

Experimental

DL-penicillamine (Sigma) was used. The following three sets of solutions (total volume 50 ml) containing 5.0×10^{-3} g-mol of potassium nitrate and the following constituents were titrated pH-metrically at $32 \pm 0.5^\circ$ under N_2 -atmosphere at 0.1 M ionic strength : Expt. 1 : (a) pH-titration of 3.125×10^{-4} g-mol of penicillamine and (b) 3.125×10^{-4} g-mol of penicillamine and 2.5×10^{-4} g-mol of $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $BeSO_4$, $NiSO_4$, $ZnSO_4$ and $CoCl_2$ against 0.05 N NaOH ; Expt. 2 : (a) water and (b) pH-titration of 2.5×10^{-4} g-mol of $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $BeSO_4$, $NiSO_4$, $ZnSO_4$, $CoCl_2$ and $CdSO_4$ against 0.05 M sodium penicillamate ; Expt. 3 : (a) pH-titration of 6.25×10^{-4} g-mol of penicillamine and (b) 6.25×10^{-4} g-mol of penicillamine and 2.5×10^{-4} g-mol of $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $BeSO_4$, $NiSO_4$, $ZnSO_4$ and $CoCl_2$ against 0.05 N NaOH.

References

1. J. H. RITSMA and F. JELLINEK, *Recl. Trav. Chim.*, 1972, **91**, 923.
2. G. R. LENZ and A. E. MARTELL, *Biochemistry*, 1964, **3**, 745.
3. R. K. PATNAIK and S. PANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 673.
4. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 1050.
5. K. K. TRIPATHY and R. K. PATNAIK, *Acta Chem. (Budapest)*, 1973, **74**, 279.
6. I. M. KLOTZ, J. M. UROUHART and H. A. FIESS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5537.
7. N. C. LI and R. A. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5225.